

Synthesis of Bifunctional Derivatives of Chalcones : Tetrahydro-1,3-thiazin-4-one and Thioether. Part-I

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The compounds containing thiazine moiety are associated with a varied range of biological activities^{1,2}. Monocyclic thiazines function as bases and are very useful synthetic intermediates. Although tetrahydro-1,3-oxazines have established chemistry, there is only sporadic reports on the analogous tetrahydro-1,3-thiazines and thiazinones¹. This prompted us to investigate the reaction of chalcones with 3-mercaptopropionic acid in an attempt to develop a simple synthetic methodology for such type of compounds.

1, 3, 5; R = H

2, 4, 6; R = Cl

Reagents : (i) $\text{HS}(\text{CH}_2)_2\text{COOH}$, C_6H_6 , $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CO}_3$ and
(ii) $\text{HS}(\text{CH}_2)_2\text{COOH}$, C_6H_6

Reaction of chalcones (1) and (2) with 3-mercaptopropionic acid in the presence of ammonium carbonate in benzene afforded (3) and (4) respectively, in excellent yield. Alternately, when 1 and 2 were reacted with 3-mercaptopropionic acid without ammonium carbonate, 5 and 6 were obtained in good yields.

Experimental

M.p.s. were determined on a Kofler hot-plate apparatus

and are uncorrected. Elemental analysis were carried out on a Carlo-Erba analyser. Ir (KBr), ^1H nmr (CDCl_3) and mass spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 621, Varian A-60 and JEOL-JMSD 300 instruments respectively.

Reaction of chalcone (1) and chlorochalcone (2) with 3-mercaptopropionic acid and ammonium carbonate. General procedure-A : 3-Mercaptopropionic acid (7.0 mmol) in benzene (15–30 ml) was refluxed for 2 h using a Dean-and-Stark water collector. The solution was then allowed to cool to room temperature and to it chalcone (2.5 mmol) was added, refluxed for 1 h and then ammonium carbonate (10 mmol) was added. The contents were further refluxed for 3 h and the progress of the reaction was monitored by tlc. Benzene was then evaporated under reduced pressure. The residue was extracted with diethyl ether, washed with 10% NaHCO_3 solution, dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 and crystallised from benzene-methanol (95 : 5, v/v) as white crystals : 3 (97%), m.p. 158° (Found : C, 62.81; H, 5.77; N, 3.48. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{23}\text{O}_3\text{NS}_2$ requires : C, 62.89; H, 5.90; N, 3.50%), ν_{max} 1 685 (CONH), 1 600 (C=C benzene), 1 450 (S-CH₂) and 1 410 cm^{-1} (C-N), δ 7.25–7.9 (10H, br m, phenyl), 6.5 (1H, br s, CO-OH, D₂O exchangeable), 5.2 (1H, br s, NH, slow D₂O exchangeable), 4.2 (1H, t, HC-C₆H₅), 3.4 (2H, d, CH₂CH-Ph), 2.6 (4H, br m, 2×CH₂ adjacent to both sulphur) and 2.3 (4H, br m, -CH₂-CO- and CH₂COOH), m/z 401 [M^+ , 15%], 385 [M^+ -NH₂, 12%], 314 [385-C₃H₅ON, 60%], 241 [314-(CH₂)₂COOH, 15%], 236 [313-C₆H₅, 20%], 209 [M-C₁₀H₁₀ONS, 55%], 196 [M-C₁₁H₁₁ONS, 30%], 192 [M-C₁₁H₁₃O₂S, 65%] and 105 [192-C₃H₅OS, base peak]; 4 (90%), m.p. 145° (Found : C, 57.84; H, 5.08; N, 3.21. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_3\text{NS}_2\text{Cl}$ requires : C, 57.86; H, 5.08; N, 3.23%), ν_{max} 1 700 (COOH), 1 680 (CONH), 1 595 (C=C benzene), 1 450 (CH₂-S) and 1 405 cm^{-1} (C-N), δ 7.3–7.9 (9H, br m, phenyl), 6.3 (1H, br, COOH, D₂O exchangeable), 5.3 (1H, br s, NH, slow D₂O exchangeable), 4.5 (1H, t, HC-C₆H₅), 3.5 (2H, d, CO-CH₂CH), 2.55 (4H, br m, 2×CH₂ adjacent to both sulphur) and 2.2 (4H, br m, CH₂CO and CH₂COOH), m/z 435 [M^+ , 12%], 392 [M-CONH, 9%], 390 [M-COOH, 5%], 362 [M-(CH₂)₂COOH, 20%], 241 [M-C₁₀H₁₀O₂S, base peak], 212 [240-CO, 30%], 209 [M-C₁₀H₉ONSCl, 60%], 195 [M-C₁₁H₁₁ONSCl, 40%] and 132 [209-C₆H₅, 20%].

Reaction of chalcone (1) and chlorochalcone (2) with 3-mercaptopropionic acid without ammonium carbonate.

Procedure-B : The reaction was performed with chalcones (2.5 mmol) and 3-mercaptopropionic acid (5 mmol) without adding ammonium carbonate following the general procedure as described earlier to yield the products : **5** (89%), m.p. 145–46° (Found : C, 68.76; H, 5.77; S, 10.19. $C_{18}H_{18}O_3S$ requires : C, 68.78; H, 5.76; S, 10.20%), ν_{\max} 1 710 (COOH), 1 690 (C=O), 1 600 (C=C benzene) and 1 450 cm^{-1} (S-CH₂), δ 7.20–7.90 (10H, br m, phenyl), 6.25 (1H, br, COOH, D₂O exchangeable), 4.56 (1H, t, HC-C₆H₅), 3.6 (2H, d, CO-CH₂CH) and 2.57 (4H, br m, S-CH₂CH₂), *m/z* 314 [M⁺, 25%], 241 [M-(CH₂)₂COOH, 22%], 237 [M-C₆H₅, 22%], 209 [M-C₇H₅O, base peak], 195 [M-C₈H₇O, 45%], 132 [209-C₆H₅, 40%] and 105 [M-C₁₁H₁₃O₂S, 97%]; **6** (85%), m.p. 140–41° (Found : C, 61.99; H, 4.91; S, 9.19. $C_{18}H_{17}O_3S$ requires : C, 62.00; H, 4.94; S, 9.20%), ν_{\max} 1 710 (COOH), 1 690 (C=O), 1 590 (C=C benzene) and 1 450 cm^{-1} (S-CH₂), δ 7.2–8.0 (9H, br m, phenyl), 5.9 (1H, br, COOH, D₂O exchangeable), 4.55 (1H, t, HC-C₆H₅), 3.5 (2H, d, CO-CH₂-CH) and 2.5 (4H, br m, S-CH₂CH₂).

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